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INFLUENCE OF MIGRATION FLOWS FROM UKRAINE ON THE FORMATION OF INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL OF EU COUNTRIES

The challenges of our time, manifested in the deterioration of the security situation in the world as a whole and in Ukraine in particular, have formed risks that necessitate a theoretical and applied analysis of the impact of migrants with different motivational attitudes on the development of intellectual capital of the EU countries, which actively perform the function of a host in migration flows.

Ukraine has a robust intellectual capital, which is confirmed by the assessment of quantitative indicators of education: relatively high indicators in the educational sphere (literacy of the population, coverage of complete general secondary and higher education), in particular, occupy worthy places (from 40th to 60th) in international rankings for assessing the level of work of higher education institutions. Regarding participation, Ukraine ranks 11th in the world regarding higher education. Almost 80% of people between the ages of 20 and 26 receive higher education; previously, this figure was even higher than 80% before the introduction of mandatory external independent evaluation [1, p. 41].

The analysis of migration processes with the participation of Ukrainians allows us to conclude that Ukraine needs to move in the mainstream direction of preserving and replenishing labor resources with highly qualified workers and talented youth. EU countries use mechanisms for mutual recognition of formal qualifications. However, this vital principle has limits built into the intersection of human and cultural capital. Institutional restrictions on the recognition of formal qualifications lead to an increase in the volume of educational migration of Ukrainian youth. Thus, the prospects for disclosure of the intellectual capital of an individual entity depend on the place of its application and vary in different institutional regimes.

It is expedient to assess the role of migration from Ukraine based on the segmentation of citizens implementing cross-border movement into voluntary and displaced people. For voluntary migrants, the factors of meeting the family's minimum needs and self-realization are dominant for refugees – self-preservation. The component of motivation, in turn, determines the algorithms for inclusion in the system of social production of

host countries. Labor migrants implement a strategy of choosing the best options for using individual intellectual capital. At the same time, refugees overwhelmingly stop at the role of consumers, exploiting the system of redistribution of GDP of EU countries.

Russia's military aggression against Ukraine has caused a shift in motivation factors, changing the generalized portrait of a Ukrainian migrant. Let us present it based on a sociological survey conducted by the Razumkov Centre [2]. The vast majority (65%) of refugees arrived in their current country of residence in March this year, and in general, from the beginning of the war to the end of April, 84%. Women predominate among refugees (93%). The most significant respondents are 30 to 39 (42%) and 40 to 49 (29%). 83% of refugees are people with higher or incomplete higher education. The most represented (among the respondents) social groups are highly qualified specialists (30%), managers of enterprises and their departments (14%), entrepreneurs (14%), skilled workers (12%), and homemakers (11%).

Ukrainian migrants, particularly young people, exert a multidirectional influence on EU countries regarding intellectual capital. The high potential of the intellectual capital of Ukrainian origin needs to be adequately applied. The relatively low level of socio-economic development and the average salary in Ukraine determine the acceptability of the dekillling strategy for Ukrainian migrants (young people not burdened with the acquired social status are more likely to choose this path). Poland, Germany, and the Czech Republic are the leading countries interested in workers from Ukraine. However, in the labor market of these countries, at the expense of migrants of Ukrainian origin, in most cases, vacancies are filled that are not related to highly skilled labor, namely packers, handypersons, tailors, drivers, builders (Poland), nurses, tilers, plumbers, electricians (Germany); industrial workers, maids, welders, electricians (Czech Republic) [3].

Structural capital at the national level is a method of stimulating innovation. It demonstrates a low degree of dependence on migration processes. It can be argued that structural capital is a set of conditions determining the prospects for using migrants' human capital. We used the Knowledge Economy Index to assess the potential impact of migration from Ukraine on the intellectual capital of EU countries. The top countries that are destinations for migrants from Ukraine have a relatively low rating on the knowledge economy index. Therefore, the economic and institutional regime does not ensure the effective use of the existing potential human capital of immigrants from Ukraine. The geography of migration from Ukraine determines the impact on the EU's intellectual capital and outlines the low return on human capital.

The armed conflict involving Ukraine as a global factor has significantly increased pressure on the social capital of EU countries. Geographical and cultural proximity between Ukraine and the EU, as well as maturity within gender relations, can be considered positive prerequisites for the transplantation of social capital of Ukrainian origin at the level of factors of national order. There is a destructive impact of refugees from Ukraine on social capital due to the strengthening of intolerance sentiments and the negative nature of the impact on social cohesion and social trust as a result of a significant deterioration in the socio-economic situation of the EU countries. The deepening of the migration crisis significantly increases the burden on the European Integration Association's entire system of institutions, resulting in a change in political attitudes. Europe today is witnessing an unprecedented rise of right-wing forces in politics.

We consider the capital of relations as a prerequisite and result of migration processes: the image of a country determines its attractiveness for migrants, on the one hand. The mass arrival of refugees from Ukraine to the EU countries hurts "conditionally dynamic" sociological factors (due to changes in socio-psychological attitudes in society, complications of socio-political integration) and "conditionally dynamic" institutional factors (due to influence on indicators of economic security).

References

1. Ukraine: 30 Years on the European Path / Yu. Yakymenko et al. The Ukrainian Centre for Economic and Political Studies named after Olexander Razumkov. Kyiv, «Zapovit» Publishing House, 2021. 392 p.

2. Настрої та оцінки українських біженців (липень – серпень 2022 р.). URL: <https://razumkov.org.ua/napriamky/sotsiologichni-doslidzhennia/nastroi-ta-otsinky-ukrainskykh-bizhentsiv-lipen-serpen-2022p>

3. Міграція в Україні: цифри і факти. URL: https://ukraine.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd11861/files/documents/migration_in_ukraine_facts_and_figures_2021-ukr_web.pdf